

Mixing and Movement: Socio-economic predictors of social contact levels before, during and after the COVID-19 Pandemic in East Zimbabwe to inform spatial modelling

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GISRUK 2024

Summary

Socio-economic characteristics such as occupation, wealth, and age may vary spatially within countries. Given that socio-economic characteristics influence the number of contacts that people have, the rate and extent of geographical disease spread will therefore vary between places. This paper demonstrates that relationship between socio-economic characteristics and the number of contacts individuals have in Eastern Zimbabwe, both prior to and during COVID-19. Typically, infectious disease models consider mobility or contact variation but rarely both. This research contributes to informing spatial models of interventions to restrict movement and mixing in epidemic contexts, including consideration of geographical variation.

KEYWORDS: social contacts; COVID-19; pandemic; Zimbabwe; sub-Saharan Africa; LMICs; infectious diseases

1. Background

Diseases spread between hosts through both space and time, so to understand and predict its spread, we must understand its transmission mechanisms. Data on the number and nature of social contacts in a human population are essential to infectious disease models, which in turn feed into outbreak prediction

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and response (Buckee, Noor and Sattenspiel, 2021). Little is known about the determinants of contact numbers beyond age. Little, too, is known about how pandemic restrictions functionally impacted the movements and mixing of populations to which they were applied. These measures likely had heterogeneous effects across space and population subgroups. Mixing patterns vary between cultural and socio-economic contexts, with age assortative mixing and higher rates of intergenerational contacts more common in Lower and Middle Income Countries (Del Fava *et al.*, 2021). Though research on social contacts was accelerated by the pandemic, the data available remain limited (Hoang *et al.*, 2019; Leung *et al.*, 2023).

We take as a case study the country of Zimbabwe where severe lockdown measures were in place between March and May 2020, (Chitungo *et al.*, 2020). Using data from individual questionnaires from 2020-21 and 2022 of the Manicaland General Population Cohort Survey (Manicaland Survey), we analysed self-reported contact patterns in east Zimbabwe to identify how socio-economic characteristics predicted contact numbers, and how COVID-19-related control measures differentially affected population subgroups. We also analysed data from 21 qualitative interviews with participants from different occupational categories to help inform how people’s social networks are constituted, and to attempt to identify typologies of low and high contact and movement individuals. The findings of this research have spatial implications because the number of social contacts people have will vary geographically based on socio-economic characteristics such as occupation (Fig 1). When modeled we anticipate seeing changes to disease spread trajectory.

Figure 1 Spatial variation in the proportion of individuals with different occupations by district according to the Zimbabwe 2012 Census (data from IPUMS 5% sample)

2. Methods

We analysed data from a population-wide survey by the Manicaland Centre for Public Health Research, between April and May 2021 which interviewed 8,500 individuals from 3,915 households in Manicaland province. Participants reported their typical number of daily weekday contacts prior to and during the first COVID-19 lockdown. To explore the size of the change in contacts pre-post lockdown, we extracted descriptive statistics on contact numbers across subgroups between periods (Table 1, Figure 1) and by contact location, then used linear multivariable regression to identify correlates of these differences (Table 2). We calculated the marginal differences when controlling for other covariates to see which differences were attributable to each population characteristic (Figure 2). Pre-pandemic median contact numbers were described by age, gender, socio-economic status, urbanicity, occupational status, and contact location. In a follow-up survey (round 9: July 2022 to March 2023), we looked at the extent to which median reported contacts were maintained when compared to previously reported levels.

3. Results

Pre-COVID-19, the total reported median daily contact count was 20 (interquartile range: 6-60), with reported contact numbers that were three times higher for men than women (male median 37, IQR 8-76; female median 13, IQR 5-44, $p < 0.001$). Contacts were higher in wealthier groups (significantly so only for those in the top quintile $p < 0.01$) and significantly lower for those aged 45 and above when compared to those aged between 15-30 years ($p < 0.001$). By site type, contact rates were significantly higher in urban areas and agricultural estates ($p < 0.001$) when compared to subsistence farming settings. By occupation, reported contacts were highest in manual labourers and students and at intermediate levels among office workers, informal traders and other informal workers. All were significantly higher when compared to the unemployed and homemakers ($p < 0.001$). The highest median number of contacts by contact location was in schools. These results can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on contacts pre-lockdown (200 maximum cut off)

Subgroup		non-lockdown Median(IQR) Obs=8060	statistic, p-val	lockdown Median(IQR) Obs=8304	statistic, p-val
Gender		20(6-60)		15(6-43)	
Male	42.2%	37(8-76)	Z= 18.20, <0.001	23(8-53)	Z= 16.64, <0.001
Female	57.8%	13(5-44)		11(5-32)	
Household Socio-Economic Status (SES)			Chi2(4)=180.06, <0.001		Chi2(4)=233.85, <0.001
Poorest quintile	22.8%	11(4-38)		10(5-25)	
Second poorest	19.7%	19(5-58)		14(6-37)	
Middle quintile	17.7%	27(6-67)		19(7-48)	
Second richest	20.9%	24(6-67)		17(6-50)	
Richest quintile	19.0%	27(6-73)	21(7-57)		
Age group (yrs)			Chi2(3)=276.15, <0.001		Chi2(3)=321.95, <0.001
15-29 yrs	40.4%	26(6-71)		16(6-47)	
30-44 yrs	29.7%	23(6-63)		18(7-48)	
45-64 yrs	22.5%	17(5-50)		14(5-38)	

65+ yrs	7.5%	7(3-17)		6(3-13)	
Site Type					
Subsistence farming	13.8%	10(4-23.5)	Chi2(4)=884.17, <0.001	10(5-22)	Chi2(4)=764.64, <0.001
Roadside trading settlement	17.7%	12(5-40)		9(5-25)	
Agri estate	22.1%	46(15-90)		29(11-63)	
Commercial centre within rural	28.4%	13(4-43)		11(5-30)	
Urban	18.0%	43(9-94)		28(9-66)	
Occupation					
Manual labor	12.2%	49(22-90)	Chi2(6)=713.69, <0.001	36(16-70)	Chi2(6)=928.14, <0.001
Students or teachers	15.8%	47(7-91)		22(6-68)	
Not employed or homemakers	45.2%	11(4-31)		9(4-23)	
Workers - retail or public service	6.8%	41(12-80)		32(13-69)	
Office workers	0.9%	31(6-69)		36(10-78)	
Informal trading	10.2%	22(6-70)		21(7-54)	
Other informal	8.8%	24(6-50)		13(6-29)	

IQR: Interquartile range. All tests of difference are chi-squared tests comparing categories of participants within each time period.

Once lockdown begun, some of the greatest reductions were seen amongst those with the greatest number of contacts prior to lockdown. For examples there were reductions for males (-14.39), students and teachers (-14.21), those aged 15-29 years old (-11.71) and individuals from agricultural estates (-19.84) and urban areas (-15.97) when controlling for other factors (Table 2, Fig 2). Office workers were the only subgroup who appeared to see an increase, but this was not statistically significant as the sample was small and Confidence Intervals (CI) too large (Fig 2).

Table 2: Margins differences in contacts non-lockdown vs. lockdown

Subgroup	Margin	t	P>t	CI_lb_95	CI_ub_95
Overall	-10.376	-27.73	0	-11.11	-9.643
Gender					
Male	-14.39	-23.89	0	-15.56965	-13.20875
Female	-7.57	-15.16	0	-8.545954	-6.589317
Household Socio-Economic Status (SES)					
Poorest quintile	-11.57	-13.84	0	-13.20948	-9.931065
Second poorest	-11.87	-13.91	0	-13.54226	-10.19723
Middle quintile	-10.25	-11.27	0	-12.03093	-8.464858
Second richest	-8.05	-9.41	0	-9.724911	-6.37308
Richest quintile	-9.96	-10.76	0	-11.77048	-8.143297
Age group (yrs)					
15-29 yrs	-11.71	-18.69	0	-12.93683	-10.48076

30-44 yrs	-10.59	-14.83	0	-11.98499	-9.18577
45-64 yrs	-9.18	-11.4	0	-10.75299	-7.59866
65+ yrs	-6.21	-4.49	0	-8.924956	-3.50199
Site Type					
Subsistence farming	-2.29	-2.14	0.033	-4.384709	-0.1877705
Roadside trading settlement	-8.8	-9.66	0	-10.59093	-7.01839
Agri estate	-19.84	-21.48	0	-21.65388	-18.03145
Commercial centre within rural	-5.02	-6.97	0	-6.434536	-3.609596
Urban	-15.97	-16.24	0	-17.8949	-14.04108
Occupation					
Manual labor	-7.19	-5.63	0	-9.693274	-4.685655
Students or teachers	-14.21	-13.51	0	-16.2705	-12.14661
Not employed or homemakers	-9.53	-16.77	0	-10.64178	-8.414395
Workers - retail or public service	-8.56	-5.71	0	-11.49739	-5.62002
Office workers	2.33	0.58	0.563	-5.567382	10.22556
Informal trading	-12.05	-9.84	0	-14.45077	-9.648666
Other informal	-13.34	-10.29	0	-15.8825	-10.80117

Fig 2: Marginal differences in contact rates from multivariate regression models comparing lockdown and non lockdown periods

When viewing how contacts varied by place, pre-lockdown contact numbers at home did not appear to vary and continued to reflect the average household size of six in the last Zimbabwe national census 2012 (IPUMS, 2022). However, a large reduction was noticeable in schools and on transport, followed by workplaces and entertainments. Though almost all individuals in qualitative interviews reported that their pre-lockdown behavior had resumed, the quantitative survey for 2022 saw participants reporting an overall lower median number of contacts than they had reported prior to the first lockdown (6:4-14).

Fig 3: Comparison between median contact rates in lockdown and non lockdown periods (for those that visited each contact location)

4. Conclusion

This study can contribute to spatial infectious disease modeling by revealing the importance of socio-economic predictors of contact numbers in an emergent context such as an agent-based simulation. When input into a model with population characteristics specified, it can reveal how underlying infectious disease dynamics can be changed by applying movement restrictions to different parts of a country where high contact, high movement populations are more dominant. For instance, the fact that those on agricultural estates, and in urban areas, as well as those working in particular occupations (e.g. labor, retail and education) have significantly more contacts than others has implications for where movement restrictions could be more effective in reducing the spread of disease. It also adds to the limited body of data available on how social contact patterns changed during and since the COVID-19 restrictions were applied in sub-Saharan Africa and in Zimbabwe in particular (Melegaro *et al.*, 2017).

The study's strengths lie in its large sample size and ability to draw information on the same population's contacts over three different time periods. Limitations to consider are recall bias and potential social desirability bias for responses on reduced contact numbers during the COVID-19 restrictions period. These points are considered when analysing the data.

Social mixing data is essential for building models that seek to replicate the transmission dynamics of infectious disease outbreaks (Walker *et al.*, 2020), and increasingly for more complex models, such as ABMs that examine policy scenarios of more fine-grained responses. When non-pharmaceutical interventions are applied such as movement restrictions and bans on gatherings, knowing the number of contacts typical of those locations is the only way to effectively estimate the impact of restrictions.

5. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Medical Research Council MR/T02075X/1 and was made possible with support from UBEL Doctoral Training Partnership, the Chadwick Trust, the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL and the Gates Foundation.

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Biographies

All contributing authors should include a biography of no more than 50 words each outlining their career stage and research interests.

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Constance Nyamukapa is Research Operations Director of the Manicaland Centre. Constance has led the field operations for the Manicaland Centre successfully since 1998 and is a leading Zimbabwean researcher on HIV in adolescent girls and young women.

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Blessing Tsenesa is a Data/Information Systems Specialist with over 12 years of expertise in Data Management within the research field. Possessing a proven track record in developing custom research data management systems, Blessing is proficient in databases and diverse technologies. Currently serving as the Data Manager at the Biomedical Research & Training Institute in Zimbabwe.

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Simon Gregson is Professor of Demography and Behavioural Science at Imperial College London and Director of the Manicaland Centre for Public Health Research in Zimbabwe. His work focusses on the social and temporal dynamics and control of HIV and other infectious diseases in sub-Saharan African populations.